
Empty Wallets, Empty Promises: Examining the Reality of Winning in India's Multi-Billion Dollar Online Gaming Sector

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ABSTRACT

Online real money games has emerged as a multi-billion dollar market, providing ease and accessibility to millions of users in India (<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/>). Fantasy sports, especially cricket, have gained immense popularity in India, thanks to the massive fan base and technological developments. The market is expected to reach a size of around \$20 billion by 2025, with fantasy cricket accounting for around 85% of the total amount. This research paper explores the development of online real money games, its effect on society, and the challenges faced by the government in regulating it. The financial risks involved in online real money games are also explored in this paper. This paper also explores the Government response to online money earning games. The paper also provides recommendations on the effective regulation of online real-money gaming platforms.

Introduction

What is Real Money Games?

Real money games are those games that allow players to play games associated with money. Real money games are designed for participants to engage in gameplay that enables them to earn actual monetary rewards based on their performance and skill.

Earning games have several key components, including:

1. Risk and uncertainty: The result is unpredictable and frequently relies on chance and probability.
2. Rewards and Prize: The player receives a cash payout or other benefits if the wager is successful.
3. Location of earning games: Games can be played online or in real-world settings.

Types of earning games

1. **Chance-Based Games** – The outcome is purely luck-based, and skill does not affect results.

Examples: **Lotteries, slot machines, roulette, dice games.**

2. **Skill-Based Games** – Requires some level of skill, strategy, or knowledge to win.

Examples: **Poker, sports betting, rummy, fantasy sports.**

Legal vs. Illegal earning games

1. **Legal Earning Games** – Regulated and licensed by governments (e.g., lotteries, casinos, fantasy sports).
2. **Illegal Earning Games** – Unregulated betting, underground casinos, or unauthorized bookmaking.

What are Online Earning Games?

Online earning games refers to betting or playing games of chance or skill for money, by using a remote device such as a smartphone, tablet, compute, or laptop with an internet connection. This includes real money games, casino games, sports betting, poker, lotteries, and fantasy team, all accessible through websites or mobile apps.

Example of online money earning gaming site, platform and application-

Real money games- Winzo, MPL, Wowzy, Zupee, Rush etc are online gaming platforms that offer a variety of skill-based games, including ludo games, candy crush games, strategy games, card games, casual games, and fantasy sports.

Casino games- Online casino games offer players a virtual gambling experience, often with real money free play options. These games are hosted on websites or mobile apps and can include everything from classic table games to modern slot machines and live dealer games.

Sports betting- some popular sports betting sites are 1xBet, Betway, Parimatch, Bet365, etc.

Poker- poker is one of the most popular cards games in the world. It involves strategy, psychology, and luck, making it exciting for both beginners and pros. Some popular poker platforms in India are PokerBaazi, Adda52, etc.

Rummy- Rummy is a matching-card game played with 2 to 6 players. The goal is to form valid sets and sequences before your opponents. It's a mix of skill, memory, and strategy, making it one of India's favourite card games. Some online rummy platforms are RummyCircle, Junglee Rummy, A23 Rummy, Taj Rummy, etc.

Fantasy team- Fantasy sports let you create your own virtual team using real-life players and earn points based on their performance in actual matches. Popular sports for fantasy gaming include cricket, football, kabaddi, and basketball. These are the completely skill and knowledge-based platforms. Some popular fantasy team platforms are Dream11, Myteam Circle, Myteam11, Winzo, MPL, etc.

Reasons Behind Popularity Of Online Earning Games-

As online money earning game is accessible from everywhere it becomes more popular from last few years. Especially the younger generation is increasingly drawn to online earning gaming and fantasy gaming. The reasons behinds why the young generations attracted towards online earning games are-

1. Easy Access- many mobile application, websites and UPI payments make it simple and easiest.
2. Misleading advertisement- many celebrities, sports person, and influencer promote the online earning games.
3. Big rewards- top rank holder gets huge price.
4. Exciting offers- Signing bonus, deposit bonus, referral bonus, and many cashbacks offers.
5. Instant withdraws- most of the online earning game platforms provides instant bank or UPI withdraws facilities.
6. Thrill and Entertainments- many popular games are provided by online earning gaming platforms.
7. Lack of Awareness – Many don't realize the risks of addiction & financial loss.

Online earning game is increasingly prevalent among young people, and studies highlight its negative consequences. The accessibility of gaming platforms, the rise of esports betting, and social media promotions contribute to its growth. However, evidence suggests that excessive gaming leads to addiction, financial problems, psychological distress, and even social isolation (King, 2016) Many young people struggle with impulse control, making them more vulnerable to gaming-related harm.

Literature Review

Year	Author(S)	Title	Objectives Of The Study	Research Methodology	Major Findings
1 Mar 2024	Andreea Raluca Duguleană, Cristina-Roxana Tanasescu, Mihai Duguleana	Emerging Trends in Play-to-Earn (P2E) Games	Establish primary drivers in web3 game development. Understand consumer decision-making in play-to-earn games.	Proposed methodology for comparing and classifying P2E games. Analysis of consumer behavior in cryptocurrency-based games.	Identified drivers influencing web3 game development and consumer decisions. Highlighted micro-economies and consumer roles in play-to-earn games.
1 Dec 2017	Navya H. Ajjar	Impact of Online Games among Young People in India	Discuss positive and negative effects of online gaming. Explore online gaming's impact on youth lifestyle and psychology.	The paper discusses the negative and positive effects of online gaming. It explores the impact of online gaming on young people in India.	Online gaming impacts youth positively and negatively. Majority of young gamers are male (83%)
24 Dec 2024	Satyam Mangala	Regulation Of Gambling in India:	Explore gambling regulation significance and historical overview.	Cost-benefit analysis of gambling legislations.	Gambling regulation impacts economic stability and addiction issues.

		A Way Forward in The Direction of Responsible and Sustainable Gambling	Analyze implications of different gambling legislations.	Examination of gambling regulation through education and scoring concepts.	Policy suggestions for production, consumption, and market regulation provided.
31 Jul 2023	Gaurav Shandilya	Exploring the Impact and Concerns of Online Gaming: A Survey-Based Study of Dhanbad, India	Explore impact and concerns of online gaming in Dhanbad. Analyze youth involvement, addiction, and gender division in gaming.	Survey-based study conducted in Dhanbad, India. Focus on impact and concerns of online gaming.	Youth involvement and addiction in online gaming observed. Economic opportunities and health concerns highlighted, including eye problems.
	Ayur Dubey, Dr. Amit Kumar	Review on the Online Gaming Industry in India	Determine the status of the Indian gaming industry. Identify factors affecting the industry's growth.	Sample survey conducted with 40 participants. Data collected from various age groups.	Majority of gamers are aged 21 to 23 years. Affordable smartphones and free internet boosted online gaming popularity.
1 Jan	Jan	Online	Analyze time spent	Online survey of	Young people spend

2012	Keilhauer	Games: Modern Media Worlds of Young People	on online gaming by youth. Explore social relationships and experiences in gaming.	young online gamers. Qualitative interviews with gamers aged 10 to 22.	significant time on online games. Social relationships are maintained through gamer groups.
10 Jul 2020	Kritika Premnath Amin, Mark D. Griffiths, Deena Dimple Dsouza	Online Gaming During the COVID-19 Pandemic in India: Strategies for Work-Life Balance.	Explore online gaming's impact during COVID-19 pandemic in India. Suggest strategies for maintaining work-life balance.	Strategies for maintaining work-life balance during COVID-19. Recommendations for healthy coping and time management.	Increased online gaming engagement during COVID-19 lockdown in India. Excessive gaming linked to mental health issues and occupational imbalance.
1 Jan 2023	Sai Prasad Ojha, M. Z. Shaikh, Manika Gupta, Anikta Sambhaji Shinde, Sahil Waghmare, Supriya Shukla	Study the Effects of Online Gaming on Different Emotional Behavior of the Users	Analyze gaming's impact on emotional behavior and focus. Examine toxicity effects on gamers' daily activities and aggression.	Intensive surveys conducted among college students. Observations and significant secondary research performed.	Gaming improves thinking but can lead to addiction. Toxicity affects concentration and increases aggression in gamers.
12 Aug	Jeffrey G. Snodgrass,	Gaming lounges in	Examine video game-related	Ethnographic observations and	Video game gambling regulated by moral

2024	Michael G. Lacy, Evan R. Polzer, Chakrapani Upadhyay	India afford socially productive gambling: The moral economy and foundations of play in Udaipur, Rajasthan	gambling in India. Analyze moral economies regulating item exchanges.	interviews conducted with players. Surveys to gather data on gaming and gambling practices.	economies in gaming lounges. Owners' values reduce excessive gambling risks among players.
17 Jul 2024	R. Deepak, Mrs. Aruna A. R.	A Study on Legalization of Betting in India, in Reference with Game of Skills and Game of Chance	Understand differences between games of skill and chance. Analyze economic benefits and gambling effects of legalization.	Descriptive study on legalization issues in India. Online survey of 203 randomly selected respondents.	Legalizing betting will benefit the economy. Monitoring money flow poses significant challenges.
1 Jan 2023	Lakshmi Vijayakumar, Vinayak Vijayakumar	Online gambling and suicide: Gambling	Define and discuss gambling disorder (GD) and its implications. Highlight the	Cognitive behavioral therapy, anonymous, and motivational	Gambling disorder linked to high suicide rates. Online gambling increases risk among

		with lives	association between gambling disorders and suicidality.	interviewing Pharmacotherapy for co-occurring disorders	young individuals.
23 Sep 2022	Alaukik Shrivastava	Resolving legal complexities and paving the way forward for the fantasy sports industry in india	Analyze importance of fantasy sports industry in India. Examine legal framework and propose effective solutions.	Doctrinal method of study employed for analysis. Reliance on case laws and expert opinions.	Fantasy sports industry can attract INR 100 billion investment. Establish a central regulator for fantasy sports legality.
	Manish Kumar	Fantasy Cricket: Gambling or Game of Skill	Explore motivations for low-income families in fantasy cricket. Analyze legality and skill versus luck debate in fantasy platforms.		Fantasy cricket revenue expected to reach 20 billion USD by 2025. Supreme Court's stance on legality revolves around skill versus luck.
6 Dec 2023	Yatan Pal Singh Balhara, Daman Deep Kaur	Fantasy Sports as Gaming or Gambling	Assess engagement attributes in fantasy sports among college students. Explore perceptions	Cross-sectional observational study among college students. Semi-structured	One-fifth of participants engaged in fantasy sports at least once. Monetary motivations

	Gulati, Akan ksha Jayant Rajguru	? Perceptio n, Attitudes, and Engagem ent Behavior of College Students	and attitudes toward fantasy sports.	questionnaire assessing sociodemographics and gaming patterns.	linked to perceptions of fantasy sports as gambling.
1 Jan 2020	Durbashree Bhattacharya, Nayana Nimkar, Pra neet Karkera	Impact of Fantasy Sports on Indian Sports Market	Analyze consumer behavior towards fantasy sports. Assess impact on Indian sports market.	Sample data collected from 297 participants. Questionnaires based on interest, knowledge, and motives.	Participants' interest in sports drives fantasy sports engagement. Fantasy sports significantly impact the Indian sports market.
1 Sep 2021	Muralee Das	Fantasy sports and gambling regulation in the Asia- Pacific	Analyze Asia- Pacific gambling market and regulations. Propose a regulatory framework for fantasy sports.	Review of fantasy sports and gambling regulation in Asia- Pacific Proposal of Nevada- model regulatory framework for fantasy sports market	Analyzed 21 countries' gambling regulations in Asia-Pacific. Proposed Nevada-model regulatory framework for fantasy sports market.
21	Raffaello	New	Review literature	Review of literature	High exposure to

Nov 2022	Rossi, Agnes Nairn	Developments in Gambling Marketing: the Rise of Social Media Ads and Its Effect on Youth	on social media gambling marketing effects. Provide direction for policymakers and scientific community.	on social media gambling marketing and its effects on children Examination of the size and impact of social media gambling advertising	social media gambling advertising among youth. Ads portray gambling as harmless, appealing to young people.
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Research Methodology

Research Design-

The study adopts a **mixed-method research design**, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to examine the financial realities of online money-earning games in India. A short survey supplied the statistics; follow-up phone calls and open-ended survey questions supplied the stories. Mixing the two gives a clearer picture of whether these apps actually leave money in a player’s pocket.

Nature of the study

The research is descriptive and analytical in nature. First we map how the leading real-money gaming apps in India work—entry fee, prize pool, rake, withdrawal rules, and the tax that is sliced off at both ends. Then we run the arithmetic to see what a typical participant keeps after every charge is paid.

Data sources

Primary data were collected through a **structured questionnaire** administered via **Google Forms**. The questionnaire included closed-ended questions related to participation, types of games played, financial outcomes, satisfaction levels, and perceived risks.

Secondary material was pulled from peer-reviewed journals, white papers published by the All India Gaming Federation, court judgments (various state high courts and the Supreme Court), and newspaper investigations on GST raids and TDS defaults.

Sample

Because no central registry of players exists, we used convenience sampling. The form was shared until 51 usable replies arrived—31 from active players and 20 from people who had never staked money online but watched friends do so. The mix lets us compare perceptions with recorded outcomes.

Analytical tools

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics—percentages and frequency counts—and presented in tables that show net gains or losses after platform commissions and tax.

Limitations of the study

The sample is small and self-selected, so the margin of error is wide. All financial figures are self-reported; we could not cross-verify bank statements.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Reality of actual winning of online games-

If two people are playing a game where each player contributes ₹10, then maximum platforms provide total prize pool is ₹ 17.6.

So, the winner gets ₹7.6. Out of which 30% is directly paid to the government. ₹2.28 (30% of ₹7.6) is paid as a tax at the time of withdraws.

And most online gaming platforms charge around **5% commission** on the total winnings at the time of withdraws. ₹0.766 (5% of 17.6-2.28) is deducted as platforms commission charge.

At the end the winner actual gets ₹4.554(17.6 –10- 2.28 – 0.766) as a winning amount.

Let’s think if player A win a game, he\ she actual earned ₹4.554. On the other hands if player A loose the game, his actual loss is ₹10. So, if the player A win the first 2 games, his/ her actual winning is ₹9.108. After winning the first 2 game if he/ she loses the third game, then his/ her actual loss is ₹0.892. So, 2:1 winning ratio make a loss ₹0.892.

Game Number	Outcome (₹)	Net Winnings/Loss (₹)	Cumulative Net Winnings/Loss (₹)
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1	Win	4.554	4.554
2	Win	4.554	9.108
3	Loss	-10	-0.892

In this example it is clear that how online gaming platforms exploit the players. The actual winning\ loss amount is increasing at same rate as increasing the contribution or boot amount.

Reality of Fantasy Team Platforms-

On fantasy sports platforms, you'll find different types of contests, including:

1. **Mega Contests** – Large contests with thousands of participants and high prize pools, often including grand prizes for top finishers. The entry fees are ₹39, ₹49, ₹99, etc.
2. **Small Contests** – Limited-entry contests with fewer participants and smaller prize pools.
3. **Head-to-Head Contests** – One-on-one matches where you compete directly against a single opponent, and the winner takes all.
4. **Private Contests** – Custom contests created by users where they can invite friends to play.
5. **Winner-Takes-All** – The top scorer wins the entire prize pool.

In mega contests, experienced players and professionals often create large number (or even hundreds) of teams, increasing their chances of winning. This makes it extremely difficult for casual players who enter with just one or two teams to win big prizes. If a casual player entering with just one or two teams significantly lowers the chances of winning a mega contest. It can feel like a waste of money and time if you're consistently losing. Many young people get addicted to fantasy gaming, hoping for a big win but often losing more than they earn.

Discuss about Small or Head-to-Head contest-

Let's an example of 4 players contest each contribute ₹89.

Elaborate the Contest:-

- **Total Investment:** ₹356 (4 players × ₹89 each)
- **Prize Pool:** ₹300 (platform keeps ₹56 as commission)
- **Winner's Earnings After Tax:** ₹147.7 (after 30% tax deduction from ₹211 profit)
- **Government Tax:** ₹63.3 (30% of ₹211)
- **Total Money Lost by Other Players:** ₹267 (3 players × ₹89 each)
- **Overall, Loss in the System:** ₹119.3 (₹356 invested – ₹236.7 received by the winner)

Metric	Amount (Rs)
Total Investment	356
Prize Pool	300
Winner's Earnings After Tax	147.7
Government Tax	63.3
Total Money Lost by Other Players	267
Overall, Loss in the System	119.3

Principal Findings:

1. **Platform Profit** – Fantasy platforms take a commission (₹56 in this case).
2. **Tax Deduction** – The winner loses a chunk (₹63.3) in taxes.
3. **Net Loss for Players** – The system ensures that more money is lost than won, making long-term profitability difficult for casual users.

The Reality:

- The odds are structured to favour platforms and the government, not players.
- The more you play, the higher the chance of losing money over time.
- Unlike stock markets or real investments, there's no way to "recover" losses except by winning (which is uncertain).

Analysis of Respondent Data:

Do you currently play any online money-earning games? (Games that allow you to earn real money through playing, betting, or competing)

51 responses

Out of 51 responses, 31 people stated they do not play these types of games.

The remaining 20 people responded that they do play them.

This means that a majority of the respondents, approximately 60.8%, do not engage in online money-earning games, while a significant minority, about 39.2%, do.

Which type(s) of money-earning games do you play most often? (Select all that apply)

42 responses

Most Popular: "Video games with cash rewards" (e.g., PUBG, Ludo) are the most popular, with 14 selections, making up about 33.3% of the total selections.

Second Most Popular: The "Other" category received 12 selections, representing about 28.6% of the total selections. This indicates that a notable portion of players are involved in game types not listed in the options.

Third Most Popular: "Fantasy sports" (e.g., Dream11, My11Circle) was selected 10 times, accounting for about 23.8% of the total selections.

Least Popular: "Quiz and trivia cash apps" (e.g., BrainBaazi) were not selected by any respondent (0 selections). "Online card games" (e.g., Rummy, Poker) were the next least popular, with only 2 selections.

"Betting/prediction apps" were selected 4 times, representing about 9.5% of the total selections.

When playing online money-earning games, what is your typical financial outcome?
47 responses

A significant portion of respondents, 21 people (or about 44.7%), stated they do not play these games.

Among all respondents, the most common response was "Sometimes I make a profit, sometimes I lose" with 11 selections (about 23.4%).

"I usually lose more than I earn" was selected by 7 people (about 14.9%), while "I break even" and "I make a consistent net profit" were selected by 5 (10.6%) and 3 (6.4%) people respectively.

Results for Players Only (26 Respondents):

Focusing on the 26 respondents who actively play these games provides a clearer picture of typical financial outcomes for players:

Mixed Outcomes are Most Common: The largest group, 11 players (or about 42.3%), reported having mixed results, stating "Sometimes I make a profit, sometimes I lose."

Net Losses are More Common than Profits: A higher number of players (7, or about 26.9%) reported that they "usually lose more than they earn" compared to those who "make a consistent net profit" (3, or about 11.5%).

Breaking Even is a Common Outcome: 5 players (or about 19.2%) said they "break even" with no significant profit or loss.

On average, how much money do you lose per month while playing online money-earning games? (This is the net amount lost after subtracting any earnings from the amount spent.)

45 responses

The total number of responses for this question was 45.

The largest group of respondents, 17 people (about 37.8%), reported a net zero or gain, indicating that they do not lose money on average.

The most common net loss amount is between ₹500 and ₹1000, with 7 respondents falling into this category. This category has the same number of selections as the "Less than ₹500" category, which also had 7 respondents. Combined, these two categories represent 14 of the 24 people who reported a net loss.

Among those who do lose money, 24 people in total, 14 (about 58.3%) lose less than ₹1000 per month.

A smaller number of respondents reported higher losses, with 5 people losing ₹1001-₹1500, 2 people losing ₹1501-₹2000, and 3 people losing more than ₹2000 per month.

Additionally, 4 people preferred not to disclose their financial outcome.

How satisfied are you with your overall experience of playing online money-earning games?

42 responses

The total number of responses for this question was 42. The satisfaction was measured on a 5-point scale, where 1 is "Very satisfied" and 5 is "Very dissatisfied."

The most common response was "Very dissatisfied" (rating 5), with 13 people selecting this option. This represents approximately 31% of the respondents.

The second most common response was "Very satisfied" (rating 1), selected by 9 people, or about 21.4% of the respondents.

The middle ratings (3 and 4) were both selected by 8 people, each representing about 19% of the total.

The lowest number of responses (4) was for rating 2, which represents about 9.5% of the respondents.

This indicates a significant divide in user satisfaction, with the highest number of responses at the two opposite ends of the scale, particularly a high percentage of very dissatisfied users.

What are the main reasons for your satisfaction or dissatisfaction? (Select all that apply)

44 responses

"Other" is the top reason: The most frequent response, at 11 out of 44 (25%), is "Other." This suggests that a significant portion of the respondents' reasons for satisfaction or dissatisfaction are not covered by the predefined options. To understand these reasons, one would need to analyze the specific free-text responses associated with this category.

Addictiveness is a major factor: The second most common reason is "The games are addictive and I..." with 10 out of 44 responses (22.7%). This indicates that the addictive nature of the games is a primary driver of either satisfaction (for those who enjoy the engagement) or dissatisfaction (for those who feel negatively about the compulsion).

Entertainment and social interaction are tied: Both "The games are entertaining and..." and "I enjoy the social interaction or..." received 8 responses each (18.2%). This shows that the entertainment value and the social aspects of the games are equally important factors for a considerable number of people.

Losing money is a significant issue: "I lose more money than I expect..." was a reason for 6 people (13.6%). This is a key point of dissatisfaction, highlighting potential issues with perceived fairness, odds, or the financial commitment required.

Lack of transparency is a concern: 5 people (11.4%) cited "Lack of transparency or fairness..." as a reason. This points to a trust issue among a notable segment of the user base.

Earning money is a minor factor for satisfaction: Only 4 people (9.1%) chose "I earn money consistently." This suggests that for most respondents, consistently earning money is not the primary driver of their satisfaction.

Withdrawal process is a minor issue: "The withdrawal process is com..." was selected by only 3 people (6.8%), indicating that while it is a reason for some dissatisfaction, it is not a widespread problem.

Customer support is not an issue: "Poor customer support or tech..." received 0 responses (0%). This is a very positive finding, indicating that customer and technical support is not a reason for dissatisfaction among any of the 44 respondents.

Conclusion

The evidence collected for this paper leads to one clear finding: online money-earning games in their present form take more from young Indians than they ever give back. Platform fees, government tax and the low chance of winning ensure that most players finish each month poorer than they started. The survey data mirror this arithmetic: a majority record steady losses, while the rest report unstable gains that never quite cover earlier defeats.

Alongside the monetary damage we observed a string of personal setbacks—compulsive play, rising anxiety, falling grades and a drifting focus on career plans. These effects are strongest among students and first-time earners, the very groups the platforms target.

Given this balance sheet, the recent moves to ban or tightly control real-money gaming appear less like moral panic and more like a sensible guard-rail. A free market in these games does not create the promised extra income; it simply redistributes small savings from many young pockets to a few company accounts.

If policy-makers choose regulation over prohibition, the rules must start with hard limits on rake rates, visible warnings that spell out expected losses, and school-level programmes that teach the basic probability of never coming out ahead. Without such steps, the industry will continue to sell an illusion of easy money while emptying the wallets and futures of India's youngest earners.

Suggestions

Tighten Implementation of the Prohibition

Authorities should apply the existing prohibition on cash-reward online games with uncompromising rigor: blacklist unlicensed domains and smartphone apps, trace and interrupt illicit payment gateways, and impose heavy sanctions on operators that exploit regulatory gaps or host their servers abroad.

Nationwide Education on Risk and Money Management

Launch sweeping information drives that warn adolescents and their parents about the hazards of “play-to-earn” platforms—specifically, the threat of financial ruin, compulsive behavior, and deceptive marketing. Embed modules on probability, risk assessment, and the mathematics of long-term loss in school and university curricula so that students can evaluate such schemes critically.

Tighter Oversight of Marketing and Influencer Hype

Outlaw or strictly limit advertising that presents online money games as effortless income, especially when aimed at minors. Impose statutory penalties on celebrities and social-media influencers who glamorize these activities, removing the illusion of quick profit.

A Youth-Centric Regulatory Compass

Policy makers should place the mental solvency and financial safety of young citizens above fiscal gains from the gaming sector. Future rules must be drafted through a social-welfare lens, not a revenue-maximizing one.

Expand Detection and Care for Gaming-Related Harm

Scale up university counselling units, toll-free helplines, and community mental-health clinics prepared to treat online-gaming dependency. Lecturers, tutors, and campus staff should be trained to spot early signs of both psychological distress and money problems linked to excessive gaming, ensuring timely intervention and sustained support.

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